

Exploration of machine-learning techniques to reproduce intra-pin power estimation from Monte Carlo calculations

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DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20803656

ABSTRACT

The information provided by state-of-the-art core simulators, relying on pin power reconstruction techniques, may, under certain conditions, not fully capture the potential presence of strongly localised intra-pin flux gradients. These gradients can significantly impact heat flux distributions and lead to considerable neutron fluence asymmetries within fuel assembly structures and materials. To overcome this limitation, consistent Monte Carlo (MC) models were developed to perform high-spatial-resolution estimates in full-core models. However, MC calculations remain computationally demanding and can require up to multiple days on limited computational resources to achieve acceptable MC uncertainty for spatially localised estimates. In contrast, certain application tasks demand faster assessment of such local estimates. This article presents an exploratory study investigating the feasibility of replacing explicit MC simulations with fast-running surrogate models based on data-driven methods for hot zero power conditions. This approach combines nodal and pin power estimates from core simulators with local intra-pin power estimates from MC calculations. The local information is used to train and test the capabilities of a surrogate model and provide fast predictions of local pin power. Based on this approach, a neural network regression achieved a mean relative deviation of $-0.36 \pm 2.04\%$ compared to MC test estimations. Such surrogate models could support nuclear power plants by complementing online system information with local intra-pin power estimates. Additionally, accurate local flux estimations could benefit the designing, monitoring, and evaluation of fuel material irradiation programmes.

Keywords: Intra-pin power, Neural Network Regression, Serpent, Simulate

1. INTRODUCTION

Under certain conditions, core simulators using pin power reconstruction may not fully capture strongly localised intra-pin flux gradients [1], which can distort heat flux and neutron fluence distributions within fuel assemblies (FAs). While high-resolution Monte Carlo (MC) models can be used to assess these spatially localised effects, they are computationally intensive and could require several days on multi-core systems to reach acceptable MC uncertainty. To enable faster assessments, this study explores, as an initial step toward a broader objective, the replacement of MC simulations (Serpent V.2.2.0) with data-driven surrogate models for an evolved cycle under hot zero power (HZP) conditions. These surrogate models are trained using combined nodal and reconstructed pin power data from SIMULATE5 V1.23.00, together with local intra-pin estimates from MC simulations. Ultimately, this approach aims to deliver accurate and near-instantaneous intra-pin power predictions (within a few seconds) across a wide range of operational conditions, using the rapidly available pin-level results from the nodal solver.

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2. INTRA PIN POWER ESTIMATION

To estimate the axially integrated intra-pin power distribution across all pins in the modelled reactor, the reference MC model detailed in [2] was employed using the PSI CHUP [3]. This full-core model consists of 177 FAs, applies no symmetry approximation, and clusters pin burnt fuel material into 25 adaptive groups [4] across 40 axial segments per FA based on spatial isotopic distributions. This clustering reduces memory consumption while reducing biases that arise from model simplifications to fit available hardware resources.

This reference model was verified against the nodal solver and demonstrated an effective multiplication factor of $k_{eff} = 1.00018 \pm 1$ pcm for the HZP conditions, with a memory requirement of 184 GB using 44 OMP threads.

To reduce statistical uncertainty in such spatially localised estimates, the reference MC model was further optimised to increase the number of batches simulated per minute. Optimisation results are presented in Table I. Since MPI parallelism causes memory duplication, OpenMP (OMP) parallelism was preferred to avoid excessive use of memory. Based on the cluster hardware characteristics, a maximum of 88 CPUs per node could be used through OMP parallelism.

The first optimisation involved excluding isotopes with negligible impact on k_{eff} , based on a sensitivity study described in [4]. This eliminated 48% of the isotopes from the original set based on all isotopes provided by the SNF code and available in the library ENDF/B-VII.1. This adjustment reduced memory consumption from 184 GB to 107 GB using 44 OMP threads and increased the batch rate by 1.8 compared to the reference MC model.

Next, the model was adjusted to utilise all 88 CPUs per computational node, increasing batch rate by 2.9 while raising memory use from 107 GB to 188 GB. Finally, a refined regular 2D cylindrical mesh illustrated in Figure 1, with 5 radial divisions and 8 azimuthal divisions per pin, was added for evaluation of the intra-pin power distribution across all pins in the modelled core. This raised memory consumption to 197 GB and reduced the number of batches per minute to 2.1 compared to the reference model.

MC model	OMP	MEM (GB)	Batches per min. compared to ref.
Reference	44	184	1
Iso. Filtered	44	107	1.8
Iso. Filtered	88	188	2.9
Iso. Filtered + intra-pin detector	88	197	2.1

Table I. Impact of isotopic filtering, CPU count, and intra-pin detector on memory use and simulation time.

Figure 1. Mesh characteristics used for intra-pin power estimation.

To ensure fission source convergence, 1,500 initial batches were discarded in optimised models compared to 200 for the reference simulation. Additionally, fission sources from converged simulations were loaded to improve the convergence of those simulations. With these modifications, the optimised model using the intra-pin detector achieved a $k_{eff} = 1.00023 \pm 1$ pcm, corresponding to an increase of 5 pcm compared to the reference MC mode. For that purpose, 47,700 batches of 500,000 particles were simulated in 7 days using 88 CPUs.

Following verification of the MC model at the pin resolution against the nodal solver [4], intra-pin power estimates were calculated using a 2D cylindrical mesh applied over the full axial length of every pin. A regular mesh was selected for its simplicity in this exploratory study. However, future studies could benefit from a radially irregular cylindrical mesh, which would equalise detector mesh cell volumes and mitigate MC uncertainty variation linked to volume differences.

This fine mesh enables detailed estimates of axially integrated intra-pin power distribution but introduces two main drawbacks.

- As shown in Table I, it reduces MC simulation efficiency and increases memory consumption.
- The detector output file size grows from 530 MB (for the 3D pin power detector only) to 884 MB when including the 2D intra-pin mesh.

The file size increase results from the number of elements evaluated in the intra-pin mesh. The intra-pin mesh was applied to all 177 FAs, each composed of 205 fuel pins and 20 guide tubes (GT). With 5 radial and 8 azimuthal bins per pin, the total number of intra-pin mesh elements reaches:

$$Dim[Intra - pinpower] = \underbrace{177}_{FA} \times \underbrace{(205 + 20)}_{pin+GT} \times \underbrace{8}_{azim.} \times \underbrace{5}_{ang.} = 1.593.000. \quad (1)$$

As noted in [5], such fine spatial resolution in MC simulations demands substantial computational resources to accurately assess the behaviour of particles within these small volumes. Furthermore, the delta-tracking algorithm is mainly used in the MC code Serpent-2 to transport particles. Consequently, the use of the track-length estimator (TLE) is not possible with default parameters, and the “integral reactions rate needs to be calculated with the potentially less efficient collision flux estimator (CFE).” That said, as mentioned in [6]: “An example of a case where the CFE may perform better than the TLE is a mesh tally with very fine spatial subdivision. Scoring the TLE requires subdividing the particle tracks into a very large number of segments, which requires additional CPU time.” Moreover, “there is usually no major difference between the two estimators in reactor physics applications, in which reaction rates are most typically scored in regions of high collision rate near the active source” [7].

The mean MC uncertainty for the intra-pin power distribution was 1.18%. This relatively high MC uncertainty results from the small mesh volume, which limits the number of particle collisions and, as a result, affects statistical convergence.

Due to the regular cylindrical mesh used, the innermost radial ring of each pin has a volume nine times smaller than the outermost. As a result, the outer ring (under a rough approximation) records nine times more particle events, leading to an expected uncertainty three times lower compared to the innermost ring. This relationship, as predicted by the central limit theorem, aligns with the trends observed in Table II.

Table II. MC uncertainty (reported as standard deviation (SD) in (%)) in function of radial ring position. Radial ring 1 corresponds to the innermost radial ring. Guide tube meshes are omitted in all reported MC uncertainties.

Radial ring, i	SD (%)	$\frac{SD(ring,1)}{SD(ring,i)}$	$\sqrt{\frac{V_{ring,i}}{V_{ring,1}}}$
1	2.15	1.00	1
2	1.25	1.72	1.73
3	0.97	2.21	2.24
4	0.82	2.63	2.65
5	0.71	3.02	3.00

To support surrogate modelling described in the next section, estimates from the innermost radial ring were excluded due to their high MC uncertainty, as shown in Table II. This approximation seems suitable in a first trial, as these mesh cells have the smallest volume and are located at the centre of the pin, where spatial self-shielding effects and limited volume suggest minimal impact on total pin power. With this adjustment, the mean MC uncertainty for the intra-pin power estimates used in surrogate modelling is reduced to 0.94%.

A second simplification involved excluding all mesh cells overlapping the guide tubes. After these

reductions, the intra-pin power “dataset” was reduced to: $\dim[\text{Intra-pin power}] = 1.116.120$.

Finally, in a usual manner, the intra-pin power dataset was randomly split for surrogate model development: 80% of the FAs (141 FAs) for training and 20% (36 FAs) for testing. The FA selection used is shown in the left panel of Figure 4.

3. IDENTIFICATION OF KEY PARAMETERS

The first step in performing surrogate modelling was to identify suitable model types. A Gaussian Process regression was initially tested but proved infeasible due to memory limitations arising from the dataset size.

Even after the simplification applied in the previous section, only methods with strong scalability could be considered. In addition, future applications may require intra-pin predictions across a wide range of operating conditions, beyond HZP, which would demand an even larger training dataset to capture varying operational conditions effects. This would involve running multiple MC simulations at various core-follow steps and aggregating their intra-pin power estimates, making the scalability problem even more challenging. Furthermore, to improve predictive performance under such conditions, convolutional neural networks may also be considered in future work to account for the inherent spatial variability of burnup and the power map as a whole, rather than treating pin power and burnup as simple scalar inputs, as will be described in the following section.

To address the constraints imposed by the dataset size, a multivariate linear regression model was first employed. This approach is computationally efficient and can estimate regression coefficients in seconds for the application case.

During exploratory analysis, key explanatory variables were iteratively incorporated based on expert knowledge and physical insights. The model’s predictive capabilities were assessed using the coefficient of determination (R^2) of the models on the training dataset. Additionally, model performance on the unseen test dataset was assessed using the residual sum of squares (RSS). Given the following notations, where y_i represents the i^{th} value from the test dataset, x_i is the corresponding set of explanatory variables, and $f(x_i)$ is the predicted value from the surrogate model, the RSS is defined as:

$$RSS = \sum_i^n (y_i - f(x_i))^2, \quad (2)$$

The selected explanatory variables are illustrated in Figure 2. Using these variables, the surrogate model achieved an $R^2 = 0.996$, demonstrating strong predictive capabilities.

As shown in Figure 2, all explanatory variables were standardised (scaled to a mean of zero and a standard deviation of one) to improve both model performance and interpretability. Categorical variables, such as whether a fuel pin is adjacent to a guide tube, were encoded using “one-hot” encoding, transforming each category into a binary vector indicating presence (1) or absence (0).

The following explanatory variables were used to predict intra-pin power:

- Power and burnup from Simulate 5, generated using pin power reconstruction methods.
- Pin and mesh positioning:
 - Pin position in the core: Absolute coordinates (X, Y)
 - Mesh position within the pin: Defined by radial and angular coordinates (r, theta)
- Proximity of a fuel pin to a guide tube:
 - A binary variable indicating adjacency to a guide tube (upper right part of Figure 2).
 - Variables, illustrated in the bottom left part of Figure 2, explicitly encoding which mesh of a fuel pin is influenced by a guide tube. Four explanatory variables of this kind were defined: pin to the left, right, below, and above a guide tube.

Figure 2. Explanatory variables selected (the example of “pin to the left” is shown out of four possibilities: left/right/top/bottom).

- Distance of a fuel pin to the reflector:
 - A “distance” variable capturing minimum Euclidean distance to the core reflector (Figure 2, bottom middle).
 - An exponential transformation of the distance, “ $Exp.distance = exp(-distance/7)$ ” empirically introduced to enhance predictions near the core periphery.

As visible in Table III, the coefficient associated with the “power” variable equals 1.018, roughly two orders of magnitude larger than any other coefficient, confirming that Simulate 5 (S5) pin power strongly drives the intra-pin model’s predictions. Moreover, while the linear model demonstrates significant predictive capabilities, interpreting individual coefficients can be challenging due to variable interactions. For instance, the positive coefficient for burnup appears non-physical, implying higher burnup leads to higher pin power. However, its relatively small magnitude and possible collinearity with other variables likely explain this behaviour.

To capture interactions explicitly, one term combining “Exp distance” and “Mesh pos. radial” was added to the model, which improved predictive capabilities. In contrast, as will be discussed in Section 4, neural networks can capture such interactions implicitly, without manual specification.

Table III. Coefficients associated to all explanatory variables used in the linear model.

S5 power	1.018e+0	Mesh pos. radial	8.848e-2	Pin next to GT	-1.361e-2
S5 burnup	6.620e-3	Mesh pos. angular	-1.863e-4	Pin to the left of a GT	6.495e-2
Pin pos. X	9.474e-3	Distance	-6.618e-2	Pin to the right of a GT	6.513e-2
Pin pos. Y	-8.983e-3	EXP distance	-1.741e-2	Pin to the top a GT	6.456e-2
		EXP distance * Mesh pos. Radial	-2.875e-2	Pin to the bottom of a GT	6.472e-2

Following this selection, to explore potential non-linearities missed by the linear model, a neural network (NN) was developed using the Keras library. The NN incorporates the coefficients of the previ-

ously introduced linear model as a fixed component and adds a residual NN to capture the remaining corrections. This residual network consists of two fully connected layers with 32 and 16 units, respectively, using tanh activations, followed by a linear output layer. The outputs of the linear component and the residual network are summed to produce the final prediction.

The network was trained using the Adam optimiser with an initial learning rate of 0.01. Training was performed for up to 100 epochs with a batch size of 205, using a 20% validation split from the training data. To improve convergence, the learning rate was reduced by a factor of 0.5 if the validation loss did not improve for six consecutive epochs, and early stopping with a patience of 50 epochs was applied, restoring the best weights. Model performance was evaluated using the mean absolute error metric. Based on this trained NN, predictions presented in the following section for the remaining 36 test FAs were generated in 8 s compared to the 7 days on 88 CPUs using the MC solver for the reference solution.

4. RESULTS

A summary of the surrogate model's prediction performance on the test dataset is presented qualitatively in Figure 3 and quantitatively in Table IV. As seen in Figure 3, both the linear regression model and the neural network yield intra-pin power predictions that align closely with the test data for values up to 1.5. Beyond this range, the linear model shows a tendency toward underprediction, while the NN continues to perform well at higher intra-pin power values. Deviations from the ideal prediction line (red dotted) are generally smaller for the NN, illustrating its improved accuracy.

Figure 3. Intra-pin power predictions vs. test data for the linear regression (left) and the NN (right).

	Linear regres.	NN
RSS	842	423
Mean rel. dev. \pm SD	0.48 ± 3.34	-0.36 ± 2.04

Table IV. Prediction capabilities of models generated.

This observation is further supported by the quantitative results in Table IV. For the $7.380 = \overbrace{36}^{FA} \times \overbrace{205}^{Pin}$ pins in the test dataset, the linear model achieved an average relative deviation $\frac{pred.-test}{test}$ of $0.48 \pm 3.34\%$. The NN further improved accuracy, with a mean relative deviation of $-0.36 \pm 2.04\%$, reducing variability by 64% compared to the linear model. The NN also reduced the residual sum of squares (RSS) by a factor of 2.0, reinforcing its superior predictive performance.

The middle part of Figure 4 presents the mean relative deviation with associated standard deviation per test FA as predicted by the NN. Mean deviations range from -2.92% to 1.30% . The colour scale, indicating standard deviation, ranges from 1.37% at the core centre up to 4.22% at the periphery. This variability may be influenced by the MC uncertainty of the estimates used to train and test the NN. Indeed, the right-hand panel of the Figure 4 shows the spatial distribution of the MC uncertainty across all FAs. Notably, a correlation of 0.88 is obtained between the standard deviations of the NN predictions and the MC uncertainty across the 36 test FAs. This correlation suggests that reducing the MC

Figure 4. (Left) Train and test FAs. (Middle) Mean relative deviation between predictions of the NN and MC test estimates \pm standard deviation per FA. (Right) MC uncertainty (in %).

uncertainty could further enhance the NN model accuracy.

Overall, the results demonstrate the NN’s capability to accurately predict intra-pin power distributions under HZP conditions based on high-resolution MC-generated training data.

Figure 5 demonstrates the application of the trained NN. Explanatory variables are provided to the NN to generate intra-pin power predictions. The left side of Figure 5 shows the pin power extracted from S5 for a test FA and used to generate predictions within seconds. As noticeable in the predictions displayed in the middle section of Figure 5, an intra-pin power gradient is visible, highlighting the value of high-resolution MC-based models for strongly localised assessment. For completeness, the relative power fraction displayed in Figure 5 was calculated through the following steps:

- Energy deposition was estimated using the MC solver with the mesh defined in Section 2.
- These estimates were then divided by the volume of the associated mesh to derive the energy deposition density per unit volume.
- The estimates were normalised to a total of 1 across the core, yielding the relative power fraction displayed in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Illustration of the capabilities of the neural network.

Since this study is exploratory and focused on evaluating ML techniques, test data points from the MC simulation are available to quantify the prediction accuracy. The right side of 5 displays the relative deviation for each intra-pin prediction within a central FA. As reported in Figure 4, this specific FA has a mean relative deviation of $-0.25 \pm 1.43\%$. In Figure 5, it can be observed that deviations lie in the range of $[-4.90, 5.10]\%$, indicating the high accuracy of the trained NN. This result demonstrates the model’s ability to generate intra-pin power estimates in seconds, eventually bypassing the need for resource-intensive MC simulations that could require multiple days to complete.

5. CONCLUSIONS

This article explores the use of machine learning techniques to accurately predict intra-pin power distribution based on Monte Carlo simulations. It first outlines the development process and hardware requirements for developing a high-resolution MC model to generate intra-pin power training data. A fast surrogate model was then built using multivariate linear regression. Through an iterative process informed by expert knowledge and physical insights, the most impactful explanatory variables were iteratively selected to improve predictive capabilities, leading to a coefficient of determination of $R^2 = 0.996$ on the training dataset.

To capture potential non-linearities, a neural network was developed using the previously selected variables. On the test dataset, the NN achieved a mean relative deviation of -0.36 ± 2.04 , demonstrating strong predictive accuracy under HZP conditions. A strong correlation (0.88) between NN prediction variability and MC uncertainty suggests that reducing the MC uncertainty could further enhance the NN performance. Additionally, more advanced NN architectures such as convolutional neural networks could be explored to further enhance predictive capabilities.

Overall, the results highlight the potential of surrogate modelling for accurate, high-resolution intra-pin power predictions. Extending this approach across various operational conditions, such as full-power conditions including short-life fission products, would require further MC simulations. It would also be interesting to investigate whether the same methodology can be applied to BWR. Ultimately, the surrogate model could support online estimation of strongly localised estimates, offering nuclear operators an advanced tool for monitoring strongly localised intra-pin gradients.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The work constitutes follow-up PSI activities to the “McBurn” project that was previously partially funded by swissnuclear.

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